

USING ORIGINAL VIDEO AND SOUND EFFECTS TO TEACH ENGLISH

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Abstract. *For English teachers, developing specialized classes for various language proficiency levels is difficult and time-consuming, but the effort is unquestionably worthwhile. In my experience, students are not as interested in language instruction when it is delivered through mechanical exercises and conventional fill-in-the-blank, true/false, and multiple-choice tests. I was motivated to think about engaging, fascinating, and significant contexts and materials by this fact. Resource books contain useful mechanical exercises and supplemental materials, many of which I use myself, but they do not inspire my students. However, I can clearly see the difference when I use creativity, especially while teaching grammar, in a way that pupils are not used to. With the use of an example lesson on teaching modals of speculation that indicate degrees of certainty (such as may, might, could, and couldn't), this article will offer an engaging method of teaching grammar using audiovisual approaches.*

Keywords: *mechanical exercises, media literacy, audiovisual approaches, authentic content, freeze framing, picture-less strategy.*

Introduction

Using media, which can be presented in a wide range of print, audio, and visual formats, is a well-known method of creating meaningful context for teaching English. Teachers must understand media and media literacy in the present information world. According to Thoman (2003), media literacy plays a significant part in educational initiatives, such as teaching second languages. Creating activities based on radio programs, television shows, newspapers, and videos is only one approach to include media into language classes. In order to incorporate television into the teaching of English as a Second/Foreign Language (ESL/EFL), Rucynski (2011) shows how *The Simpsons*, a well-known American animated TV series with over 400 episodes, may be used to teach a range of English topics. As Bedjou (2006) point out that it is well accepted that language is better acquired or learned where the focus is on interesting content, and radio can certainly provide interesting content, and radio programs are also a great source of teaching ideas. Bedjou (2006) highlights the importance of radio as an English teaching tool and presents a variety of English teaching activities that can be planned around radio programs, particularly VOA Special English programs: “Radio can bring authentic content to the classroom, especially in the EFL environment, where it may not be easy to meet and talk with native speakers of English”. Another reliable and accessible source of educational content is newspapers. Newspapers are useful teaching resources because of their accessibility, cost, and relevance, according to Pemagbi (1995).

Incorporating media in language learning

Incorporating videos into lessons produces captivating images and a unique interactive setting in the EFL/ESL classroom. Using videos to teach English also gives teachers more freedom to be creative in their lesson plans. The visual representation that videos offer students of otherwise abstract subjects is one of the most effective ways that they can be included into classes, according

to Cundell (2008, 17). For my intermediate students, this concept led me to deliver a one-hour “Modals of speculation” lesson using a homemade film. With the help of videos, I was able to give my students audiovisual cues that helped them understand these crucial modal auxiliaries. Instead of searching for a video online, I decided to take on the challenge and create a brief video for the class. Importantly, I am not a specialist in recording videos, but I am proficient with my camcorder.

Preparing the video

I made a speculative context film in order to establish the ideal setting for teaching modalities of speculation. I started by asking someone to record me as I was getting ready to leave the house for work, performing actions that produced various sounds. These scenes comprised:

- using an electric toothbrush to brush my teeth

- blow drying my hair

- using a steam iron for my clothes

- boiling water in a kettle

- pouring water into a cup

- toasting bread in a toaster

- leaving the tap dripping

- using an air freshener

- leaving my cell phone ringing

- locking the door

- waiting for a lift

- getting into the car

- turning on the engine of the car

A close companion of mine followed me about and took notes while I was doing all of this. By carrying the camera and recording yourself, you can still create the video even if you do not have somebody to record it.

Options for video transfer

You can use a digital camera or even your smartphone to capture the video if your class has a computer and a video projector, or if you have access to a computer lab. After that, all you have to do is slide the memory card from your camera (or smartphone) into the memory stick slot on your laptop, slide your USB into the USB slot on your laptop, and move the video from the memory card to the USB. If the video file is not too large, you can also send it as an attachment to your personal email account. We rely on a TV and a video player to play the videos, so when I finished filming, I brought my camcorder to a nearby store to get the footage converted to a VHS videotape format.

Configuring the video lesson

When employing movies and videos in listening exercises, Harmer (2007) recommends a range of viewing strategies, such as:

- Playing the video silently (without sound);

- Asking students to predict what they anticipate will happen next while the image is frozen is known as "freeze framing";

- Viewing partially (with a piece of paper covering the majority of the screen);

- Speech or picture (half of the class faces away while the other half watches the video);

- Movies with subtitles so that students can see and hear English;

- Hearing the audio before viewing the video is known as picture-less listening.

I utilized the picture-less strategy to grab my students' interest by having them first listen to the video's audio. Students listen to the movie and make educated guesses about the origins of the sounds they hear in order to concentrate on modals of inquiry. Their curiosity is stimulated and they are encouraged to make assumptions.

When a TV set is accessible in your classroom, you can use this picture-less listening strategy in three different ways, as noted by Harmer (2007). That is, either you can turn the screen away from the students, or cover it with a piece of paper, or completely lower the brightness control. You can just switch off the projector and ask your students to listen to the sound if your classroom has a computer and a video projector. To prevent the students from seeing the film, you can also keep the projector on and reduce the window size. You can also ask the students to sit with their backs to the screen or to relocate their seats so they can just listen to the sound without opening their eyes.

Before the session started, I covered the entire screen with newspaper because I wanted to establish a speculative atmosphere right away. Students were drawn to the sight of a covered TV as soon as they walked into the classroom, and they started wondering why it was covered. They all seemed shocked, and I could tell they were curious as to why I had covered the TV. They began exchanging words and speculating as to why I had done that. A few students even questioned me about why the TV was covered. I told them to wait a moment to find out, which aroused their interest even more. I gave the students a few minutes to chat since they were so thrilled and the class activities were assisting me in creating the desired environment.

Delivering the video lesson

I started by telling the students that I had covered the TV because they were going to hear a sequence of sounds and had to guess where they came from. The students were captivated. As I played the videotape's audio, I invited everyone to write down their thoughts. I played the first scene and asked them to identify what the sound was in order to demonstrate the process and ensure that everyone understood the directions. I then went on, stopping for roughly 15 seconds at the conclusion of each scene to give everyone time to take notes. I kept doing this until they had watched the entire video. As everyone reviewed their notes, I then re-played the video. Students then divided into pairs and talked with their partners about their notes for three minutes. Students took pleasure in sharing their wildly divergent theories regarding the source of the sounds they had heard.

After then, the students watched the film again. This time, however, they talked about their thoughts together after each scene. I played the movie again after confirming that everyone had grasped the directions, stopping at the conclusion of each scene to ask them to name the sound. I prompted them to employ the proper grammar structures by posing queries. For example, I said, "What could it be?" while I acted out the scene where I was blow drying my hair. "Is that a vacuum cleaner?" While one student stated that it could be a vacuum cleaner, another replied that it could not be. I encouraged them to employ the modal construction when they were unable to use the structure by posing tag questions such "It cannot be a vacuum cleaner, can it?" Students were required to use the teaching point in order to answer my question.

I got their responses and scribbled them on the board, such as "It might be a vacuum cleaner" or "It cannot be a washing machine" To assist them notice the new structure, I then highlighted the "modal + verb to be" with a different color. I carried on the discussion about the sources of all the noises in the video and created a list of their hypotheses, which I displayed on

the board with the modals and the new structure highlighted. I then let them watch the full video after taking the newspaper off the TV screen. Because the students enjoyed themselves so much and laughed at some of their conjectures, this was the most engaging portion of the session. Lastly, I asked the students which of these structures was used to communicate possibility, probability, certainty, and impossibility. I then placed these phrases on the board just beneath the underlined structures to help them understand where each of the modals on the board may be utilized. I inquired, for example: When do we typically use “must + be”? When we are sure of something, do we use it? Or do we employ this when we believe something is feasible? “When we are sure about it,” a few youngsters remarked. Next, directly beneath the structure, I wrote “certainty” on the board. I concluded by going over the new structures with the students, explaining how to use them and responding to their inquiries.

Suggestions for alterations

The concept of video and sound effects lessons can be applied to teach a wide range of ESL/EFL students a number of subjects, including vocabulary, grammar, and creative writing.

Teaching grammar

Using the freeze frame approach, the same movie may be used to teach a variety of grammar concepts, including the present and past simple, present and past progressive, future simple, and “going to + infinitive” without to. You must play the video, freeze frame the image after each scene, and then pose questions to teach grammar. For example, ask your students, “What is s/he doing?” while freezing the image. “What did s/he do?” “What did s/he do?” “What will happen next?” or “What is s/he going to do next?” Students will be encouraged to use the teaching point in this way. After you get their responses, write them on the board and emphasize the verb structure (for example, “will + infinitive” without to for future simple, or “to be + ing” for present progressive). Students can also be introduced to and practice adverbs like *first*, *second*, *finally*, *before*, and *later* because the movie follows an action sequence.

Teaching vocabulary

You can utilize the same video that I used with my students to teach vocabulary related to kitchen and household appliances by recording sounds and asking students to determine where they came from. You may also record a range of fascinating sounds with the camera while being mindful of people’s privacy by moving it about the classroom or even outside. For instance, you could record the noises of the lunchroom, the intermission between classes, or the students playing during recess. Then, you could play the video for your students and ask them to pinpoint where the sounds started. Another option is to capture the sounds in a crowded coffee shop, a nearby subway station, or a bustling mall and use the recordings to play a guessing game with the students. You may even use your camera to film the butcher chopping or grinding meat or the cashier opening the register and giving you your change to teach terminology related to various occupations.

Asking your students to make videos is another intriguing variation. For instance, you could invite them to record sounds when they are having a picnic or engaging in another weekend activity. You can use these movies as a resource to teach vocabulary and grammar. You can offer your students the opportunity to capture sounds using their MP3 and MP4 players if you believe they might not have access to a camera.

Teaching writing

You can use the same movie that I used in my class as a visual trigger for writing tasks at various English proficiency levels. “Our students have a much richer imagination for what we might accomplish with the visual than our journals have yet to address,” as George (2002) notes. Videos can be used in writing classes by showing them to students using the picture-less listening technique and asking them to compose a narrative based on the sounds they hear. The music is a powerful auditory cue for writing, so you do not even have to play the video for them. Asking your students to record random scenes in their environment and bringing the footage to class is another option. After watching the films together, they might come up with stories that go along with them.

Conclusion

Since our daily lives are the ideal source of inspiration for developing engaging lessons and activities, finding relevant teaching materials is not that difficult. Expensive and sophisticated teaching aids are not always necessary for a successful session; frequently, disrupting the routine will engage students, excite them, and show them how language is actually used in context. Therefore, looking around and never undervaluing their sense of creativity is one of the simplest and least expensive ways for teachers to create the most effective teaching materials.

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